

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT
GPR	11	B		Min: 62.8609 Max: 62.9251	1422 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input type="checkbox"/> Anthropic

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 1851-1853 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: Fill of cut 1421 in Room 6
 Covered by: SU: 1327 Fills: SU: 1421 Filled by: SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction
 FORMATION PROCESS: Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery m <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles r <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick r <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mortar r <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Coins r (1) <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) m <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <input type="checkbox"/> Iron slag	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) m <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Charcoal f <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones r <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth r <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Shells r <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	clay 15% silt 75% sand 10% <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive Compaction: <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft Color: <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)
 Northern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original
 Southern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Western Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Eastern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1327	Covers:
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills: 1421

OBSERVATIONS: Δ434 BRONZE COIN (BUT ACTUALLY IN ADJACENT MODERN FILL 1444)

DESCRIPTION
 Position within sector: south-west, IN/NEAR ROOM 6, past 2010 excavation limit
 Shape: oblong blob (irregular), round

For layers complete this section:
 Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions): small rubble in southern end
 Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):
 Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):
 Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

Floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

During excavation this fill seemed to have covered only the northern part of the cut, thus the modern soil to the south was given its own SU 144 and equated w/ SU 137.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	SJL	on	July 21 st 2011
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